

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF ENERGY OF ACTIVATION VALUES AGAINST SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS

Substituent parameters	Corr. coeff.	Slope	Intercept
σ_p	0.9967	43.96	79.81
σ_p^+	0.8423	55.07	46.42
σ_I	0.6582	27.88	68.81
σ_R	0.6118	69.37	87.00

halides are almost independent of the substituents in the benzene nucleus of anilines (179.7–193.2 kJ mol⁻¹) for X=H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl, 4-Br and 4-OCH₃.⁷ The observed systematic variations of E_a values with substituent parameters show that the reactivity in the solid state reactions is dependent on the changes in the electronic effects of the substituents as have been previously observed in the solid state reactions of zinc and cobalt acetate with aniline hydrochlorides¹.

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Spin-trapping of Free Radical Intermediates formed during the Photo-oxidation of Aldehydes and Ketones by Hexachloro Palladate(IV) and Iridate(IV) Ions

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THE use of radical addition reactions to detect short-lived radical intermediates was first proposed by Janzen in 1965¹. Since then this technique for which Janzen and Blackburn² coined the name 'spin-trapping' has been developed extensively³. The recent surge in interest in the long established problem of photoreduction of platinum group metal salts⁴ has prompted us to report a detail spin-

trapping and matrix isolation epr study of photo-oxidation of various alcohols by hexachlorometalate(IV) ions (M=Pt, Pd and Ir)⁵. In this communication, the initial results of the photo-oxidation of some aldehydes (formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and propionaldehyde) and ketones (acetone, methyl ethyl ketone and diethyl ketone) by hexachloro palladate(IV) and iridate(IV) ions have been reported.

Experimental

The details of the epr spin-trapping experiments are the same as described earlier^{5,6}. α -Phenyl-tert-butyl nitron (PBN) and sodium-2-sulphanatophenyl-tert-butyl nitron (SPBN) (Aldrich) were used as spin-trapping agents in neat organic and aqueous organic substrate solutions respectively. 18-Crown-6(1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaoxacyclo-octadecane) was added to the solution in pure organic substrates to solubilise the inorganic salts. Aldehydes and ketones (B.D.H.) were used as such except formaldehyde, which was purified⁷ to remove the traces of methyl alcohol.

Results and Discussion

The free radical intermediates produced in these photo-redox reactions react with either of the spin-traps (PBN or SPBN) to produce the corresponding spin adducts. The epr spectra (Fig. 1) of nitroxides, the spin adducts thus produced, exhibit the characteristic primary main triplet due to ¹⁴N and the secondary doublet splittings due to β -hydrogen. The magnitudes of the hyperfine splitting parameters of the different spin adducts (Table 1) suggest that the carbon-centred free radicals are formed in these reactions. This can be attributed to the direct attack of the photo-excited hexachlorometalate(IV)

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of spin adducts of CH₂CHO with (upper) PBN obtained on the photolysis of (PdCl₆)²⁻ in neat acetaldehyde solution and with (lower) SPBN obtained on the photolysis of (IrCl₆)²⁻ in 50% aqueous acetaldehyde solution.

TABLE I—HYPERFINE SPLITTING CONSTANTS OF SPIN ADDUCTS*

Substrate	Radical trapped	Hyperfine splitting constants (mT)			
		$(\text{PdCl}_6)^{2-}$		$(\text{IrCl}_6)^{2-}$	
		a_N	a_H	a_N	a_H
Formaldehyde	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HO}$	(a) 1.40	0.32	1.41	0.31
		(b) 1.50	0.60	1.51	0.58
Acetaldehyde	$\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{HO}$	(a) 1.48	0.34	1.40	0.35
		(b) 1.52	0.61	1.53	0.60
Propionaldehyde	$\text{CH}_2\dot{\text{C}}\text{HCHO}$	(a) 1.39	0.32	1.41	0.31
Acetone	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$	(a) 1.38	0.32	1.39	0.32
		(b) 1.50	0.60	1.51	0.62
Methyl ethyl ketone	$\text{CH}_3\dot{\text{C}}\text{HCOCH}_3$	(a) 1.42	0.35	1.40	0.31
Diethyl ketone	$\text{CH}_3\dot{\text{C}}\text{HCOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$	(a) 1.41	0.31	1.42	0.30

* (a)=PBN, (b)=SPBN (spin trap was used in 50% aqueous solutions)

ion upon the C-H bond of the substrate molecule, followed by the hydrogen abstraction step (equations 1-3).

(Free radical)

(PBN)

The photolysis of $(\text{AsPh}_4)_2(\text{MCl}_6)$ ($\text{M}=\text{Pd}$ or Ir) in CH_3CN yielded $\text{Cl}^\cdot$ atom adduct with PBN⁵ with coupling constants in excellent agreement with those reported in the earlier study⁸. This suggests an alternative route (eqns. 4 and 5) for the formation of carbon-centred radicals in these reactions.

However, the addition of small quantity of acetone (~1%) to CH_3CN solution (prior to photolysis) resulted in complete loss of the $\text{Cl}^\cdot$ adduct and production of adduct of $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$. This can be explained by the nucleophilic reaction of $\text{Cl}^\cdot$ adduct with neat acetone, viz. equation (6) which parallels the proposed hydrolysis of the same $\text{Cl}^\cdot$ adduct by

water in the photolysis of $(\text{PtCl}_6)^{2-}$ in water⁸

The formation of carbon-centred free radical intermediates has been further confirmed by the cryogenic wide-band photolysis ($\lambda > 300 \text{ nm}$) of hexachlorometallate(IV) ions in the neat acetone solution at 77 K. The resulting epr spectra (Fig. 2) gave rise to

Fig 2 Epr spectra obtained on photolysis of (upper) $(\text{PdCl}_6)^{2-}$ and (lower) $(\text{IrCl}_6)^{2-}$ in neat acetone solutions at 77 K.

two principal sets for species, namely, matrix-derived $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$ ($a_{\text{H}}=2.15$ mT; $g=2.0043$) and Pd^{III} paramagnetic centre at $g=2.184^9$. However, the photolysis of hexachloroiridate(IV) ions in acetate gave only the organic radical, $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$ ($a_{\text{H}}=2.14$ mT) but no low-field absorption attributable¹⁰ to Ir^{II} as Ir^{III} is diamagnetic.

Thus, these preliminary studies support the formation of carbon-centred free radical intermediates by hydrogen atom abstraction mechanism (equations 1 and 2).

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Synthesis of 5,6,7,8,2',4',5'-Heptamethoxyflavone (Agecorynin-C)

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QUIJANO and Calderone¹ isolated several new highly oxygenated flavonoids from *Ageratum corymbosum* Zucc. These are agecorynin-A (1) and agecorynin-B (2) and the flavones agecorynin-C (3) and agecorynin-D (4). But synthetic evidence has not been adduced so far in support of the structures assigned to these products. The present paper deals with the synthesis of agecorynin-C (3) by an unambiguous and simple route.

To embark upon the synthesis of 3, 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene was the starting material, which was prepared by following the method of Baker². On Friedel-Crafts acylation, 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene afforded 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (5), which on Elb's persulphate oxidation yielded 2,5-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (6). Methylation of 6 with diazomethane gave 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (7) which on treatment with 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzoyl chloride yielded the corresponding ester 2-(2',4',5'-trimethoxybenzoxyl)-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (8). The ester (8) on reaction with KOH in dry pyridine underwent Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to produce 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (9) which on subsequent cyclisation with fused sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid medium afforded a product which was identical (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with the natural sample of agecorynin-C (3).

1; R=H
 2; R=OCH₃

3; R=CH₃
 4; R=H

5; R=R¹=R²=H (6); R=R¹=H, R²=OH
 7; R=R¹=H; R²=OCH₃
 8; R¹=H, R²=OCH₃, R=CO(C₆H₂)(2,4,5-trimethoxy)
 9; R=H, R²=OCH₃, R¹=CO(C₆H₂)(2,4,5-trimethoxy)

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were run at 100 MHz using TMS as internal standard.

2,5-Dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (6): To a stirred mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (11.2 g) and sodium hydroxide (20.0 g) in water (120 ml) was added during 4 h a solution of potassium persulphate (17.6 g) in water